

Parental Involvement in Relation to Learners' Performance

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Abstract:

The foundation of the parent's involvement in their child's education is essential. Parents' major obligation is to raise their children to become productive and responsible citizens. The key purpose of this study is to investigate the level of parental involvement in relation to learners' performance as perceived by 120 respondents in a public elementary school of a large-sized division in Central Visayas. Descriptive, relational, and quantitative research was conducted, and used a 30-item survey questionnaire as a tool to gather data on the involvement of parents in children's reading and learning activities. The results revealed that the level of parental involvement in the areas of home learning environment and parent-teacher communication was moderate, whereas in the area of family support system, it was high. The level of learners' performance was at the instructional level. There was a significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the area of the home-learning environment when compared according to age. There was a significant difference in the level of parental involvement in all three areas when compared to grade level. Further, there was a significant difference between the level of parental involvement and learners' performance. This calls for school authorities to design programs and activities that would increase parents' involvement in their children's school life.

Keywords: Academic achievement, learners' performance, parental involvement

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The School Reading Program is one of the flagship programs of the Department of Education, wherein its purpose is to intensify the schools' advocacy for reading to make every learner a reader at their grade level (DepEd Memo 173, s. 2019). However, some parents hesitated to participate in school reading program orientation and during the implementation as they thought it would burden their busy schedules. Also, some parents refuse to let their children attend because it would add to their financial burden (Benedicto, 2023).

Parental involvement plays an effective role in inculcating reading habits among children because it is the first and main strength to boost and stimulate learning potential by developing the constant habit of reading (Ahmad et al., 2020). Hence, the learners need a family support system, a conducive home learning environment, and regular communication between parents and teachers to help them reach their potential as emerging readers. Furthermore, the Department of Education strengthens the engagement of parents in their child's education by promoting a harmonious, active, and collaborative engagement among teachers, parents, and the community in the implementation of school programs for learners' welfare (DepEd Order no. 013.s 2022).

In the present research location, parental involvement is one of the issues among educators in public elementary schools. After conducting Phil-IRI, an assessment tool composed of a set of graded passages administered to individual students designed to determine the pupil's reading level (DepEd Order no. 014 s. 2018) on 35 pupils in the researcher's class, 2 were identified as non-readers; 13 were at frustration level while 12 were instructional, and another 2 were independent. Poor reader learners may continue to rise if the parents do not actively involve themselves in their children's reading activities. The researcher noticed that most parents seldom communicate with the teachers. In addition, there are testimonies from other classroom advisers that only 50% of the actual parents participate during parent-teacher meetings. Hence, teachers did not get the chance to meet the parents to know the status of their children in class or any problems inside the school. This is the reason why certain learners continued to be a problem in the school's reading intervention programs. Moreover, there was less family support system provided to the learners. Most of the parents don't show up because they are working, busy with household chores, and no one attends to the needs of their young child.

In the rationale, the researcher who is currently teaching in the above-mentioned locality would like to undertake worthy research that will benefit the school he is currently teaching and his graduate program. This study evaluates parental involvement in learners' academic performance. The result of this study may help school administrators

manage parents' involvement in reading activities at the school. Furthermore, this study aims to offer recommendations to enhance parents' involvement in reading activities aimed at improving learners' academic performance.

Current State of Knowledge

Parental involvement significantly influences students' academic success by improving performance, boosting attendance, and enhancing test scores (Tran et al., 2020; Castillo et al., 2020). Engagement may take many forms, such as helping with homework, maintaining contact with teachers, and participating in school activities (Cusinato et al., 2020; Romero et al., 2020). A major component of this involvement is the home-learning environment, which includes all interactions and resources within the home that support a child's development and education (Hill, 2018; Kapur, 2018). A supportive environment promotes motivation, focus, and emotional well-being, while conflicts and lack of resources can hinder learning (Kudari, 2016; Khan et al., 2019; Bosmion & Chua, 2020). Active parental roles in supplying educational materials and guidance directly contribute to students' academic outcomes (Kavousipor et al., 2019; Alramamneh et al., 2023).

Equally important is parent-teacher communication, which strengthens home-school partnerships and aligns educational goals (Bacsikai, 2020; Perlusz et al., 2012). Regular, open communication ensures parents are informed and involved, fostering a more inclusive and collaborative learning environment for students (Major, 2023; Popovska et al., 2021). Communication methods include meetings, digital messaging, and involvement in school programs (Szóllósi, 2022; Ozmen et al., 2016). Barriers such as time constraints and cultural differences can limit this involvement, but schools are encouraged to use various media to keep families engaged (Hakyemez-Paul et al., 2018; Smokoska, 2020). Finally, a strong family support system enhances educational outcomes by providing emotional, financial, and logistical support, which nurtures reading habits, academic motivation, and overall student well-being (Capotosto et al., 2017; Hurley & Huscroft-D'Angelo, 2018; Shahzad et al., 2020; Purwandari, 2023).

Parents are the first teachers of their children, shaping their early learning experiences, including basic skills such as reading and numeracy (Canonizado, 2021). A positive home-learning environment plays a crucial role in fostering academic achievement, as it provides the necessary resources, support, and conducive conditions for studying (Archaya, 2017; Kapur, 2018). A home that is free from distractions, provides necessary materials, and fosters positive family dynamics enhances students' ability to focus and perform academically (Manlangit et al., 2020). Furthermore, a good home environment promotes the development of positive attitudes toward learning, contributing to the acquisition of essential skills and better academic outcomes (Javier & Jubay, 2019). When parents engage actively in their children's education, the impact on their academic success is more pronounced, including the improvement of reading skills and overall study habits.

Parent-teacher communication is another vital factor in supporting students' academic success. Effective communication between parents and teachers strengthens their partnership, helping them align their expectations and strategies to support the child's learning (Pascua & Dulos, 2020). Open lines of communication, including regular updates, meetings, and shared activities, enable both parties to work collaboratively toward the child's educational goals (Javier & Jubay, 2019). This partnership not only enhances student engagement but also fosters a positive relationship between the child, parents, and educators, which contributes to improved academic performance (Kumar, 2024). Additionally, the family support system is essential in promoting students' motivation and psychological well-being. When parents provide emotional and academic support, students are more likely to succeed in their studies and feel more confident in their academic abilities (Moneva & Gonzaga, 2020; Leander & Fabella, 2020). Parental involvement shapes a child's academic development, instilling a strong foundation of skills and resilience that contributes to long-term success (Perocho & Bantolo, 2023).

Students' academic performance is influenced by factors beyond their personal characteristics, including their background, learning environment, parental support, and the availability of resources (Rabia et al., 2017). Research shows that students with stronger reading skills tend to perform better academically (Epeçan, 2018), and those with more supportive and involved parents achieve higher academic outcomes (Shahzad et al., 2020). A negative home environment, such as distractions from siblings, poor living conditions, and psychological stressors, can hinder students' ability to focus and perform well academically (Bocar & Tizon, 2017). Conversely, a positive learning environment, coupled with access to teaching materials, competent teachers, and strong parental and teacher support, plays a significant role in improving students' performance (Abaidoo, 2018).

Learners' performance, defined by the knowledge gained and assessed through marks, continuous assessments, or examinations, is influenced by various factors such as intellectual level, character, motivation, competencies, interests, study habits, self-esteem, and the teacher-student relationship (Leander & Fabella, 2020; Perocho & Bantolo, 2023). Parental involvement plays a significant role in academic achievement, particularly as parents support their children through different assessment methods used by schools, replicating these approaches at home to reinforce learning (Orillosa, 2015). The quality of learners' performance is shaped not only by family factors but also by the teaching methods and instructional quality provided by educators (Lansangan et al., 2015). Additionally,

specific academic areas, such as reading comprehension and word recognition, have been found to be at the instructional level for many students, indicating areas that require further development (Bohol, 2024; Calantas, 2020).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored on Sociocultural Theory (SCT). Vygotsky (1978), as one of the greatest psychological exponents, has contributed to the importance of parents' involvement in children's academic field. According to Vygotsky (1978), students perform a certain action under someone else's guidance or influence and can do so autonomously. For Vygotsky, the acquisition of learning occurs in this area where students go from a guided task to an autonomous task. Vygotsky (1978) comments that children acquire learning through social interaction that includes their family, school, and daily context. This indicates that parents must be involved in academic development. According to Vygotsky (1978), the instructions given in the educational and family context make the child internalize and understand new information, make it habitual, and increase his learning and ability to acquire it. This is achieved through the connection between his theory and the ties between the social contexts surrounding the child, where parental influence is seen as one of the main ones.

With this framework, for Vygotsky, the influence of parents is a main agent of interaction that allows the acquisition of learning and academic achievement. All those theories cited by Vygotsky about parental involvement perspectives contribute to our current study because they give support to what parents think about their role to make them aware of their level of participation and to have a deeper understanding of parental involvement that many times is related just with helping students with tasks at home.

As linked in the present study, the researcher believes that Parental Development Theory is suitable as the study's theoretical background. Parental Development theory highlights how a parent becomes involved and supports a child's education. Supportive parents provide encouragement and emotional warmth to their children. Learners who have supportive parents also tend to have a high level of reading development. With the essence of this theory, the researcher finds it complete to support and justify the contents of the present study.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the level of parental involvement in learners' performance in a public elementary school of a large-sized division in Central Philippines for the School Year 2023-2024 as the basis for a reading intervention plan. Specifically, this seeks to answer the following questions: 1) is the profile of the respondents according to age, highest educational attainment, grade level, and number of children; 2) the level of parental involvement in terms of home-learning environment, parent-teacher communication, and family support; 3) the level of learners' performance for the school year 2023-2024; 4) the significant difference in the level of parental involvement when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; and 5) the significant relationship between the level of parental involvement and learners' performance.

Methodology

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive research design to determine the level of parental involvement in relation to learners' performance in a public elementary school of a large-sized division in Central Philippines for the School Year 2023-2024 as the basis for a reading Intervention plan.

According to De Belen (2015), descriptive design is appropriate for studies that aim to find out what prevails in the present conditions, processes and effects, and developing trends. It is also used to determine the extent of the relationship of one variable to another variable. Likewise, it aimed to gather information about the characteristics within the present study, and it helped in making professional judgments.

A descriptive research design is appropriate since the present study also aimed to find out the prevalent conditions and gather information about parental involvement and its influence on learners' performance.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study were 120 key stage 2 parents from a total population of 173. Since the number of respondents is quite large, stratified sampling and random sampling techniques were used, and the Cochran formula was used to find the sample size. To get the percentage, the respondents coming from each grade level are divided by the total number of respondents and multiplied by the sample size. The researcher randomly selected the respondents from each school using the lottery technique.

Instruments

This study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire. The researcher made a questionnaire that has two parts. The first part comprises the personal profile of the parents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, grade level, and number of children. The second part of the questionnaire answers the level of parental involvement. The level of parental involvement is split into the areas of home-learning environment, parent-teacher communications, and family support system. It is composed of 10 items per area with a total of 30 items. The respondents were asked to rate each item using the five-point Likert scale, which contains the following scores: 5 – Always; 4 – Often; 3 – Sometimes; 2 – Rarely; and 1 – Almost Never. The research instrument was subjected to validity (4.74-excellent) and reliability (0.872-good). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively.

Data Gathering Procedure

For the smoother conduct of the study, the researcher employed the following procedures. The researcher sent a letter of request for the conduct of the study to the Office of Schools Division Superintendent. Upon approval, a separate letter was also sent to the school head of the subject school, which is attached to the approved letter from the superintendent. After granting permission, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaire to each respondent. Each item is scrupulously translated to Sinugbuanong Binisaya for convenience. The purpose of the study was properly explained, and a letter of parent consent was given to the respondents ahead of time through the learner. The researcher ensured that there would be no distractions in the classes. The researcher conducted the instrument during the PTA meeting to elicit the majority of the parents' attendance. The researcher gave the respondents enough time to ensure that all items in the questionnaires were answered. The researcher personally retrieved the questionnaires after the allowed time was passed to ensure a 100 percent retrieval of the checklist and questionnaires. Nonetheless, if parents bring the questionnaire to their respective houses, they can do so with a one-week leeway buffer room for submission.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and frequency and percentage to determine the profile of the respondents according to age, highest educational attainment, grade level, and length of service.

Objective No. 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of parental involvement.

Objective No. 3 also used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of learners' performance.

Objective No. 4 used the comparative analytical scheme and mean to determine the significant difference in parental involvement level when grouped and compared according to the variables.

Objective No. 5 used the relational analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test and Kruska Wallis H test to determine the relationship between parental involvement and learners' performance.

Ethical Consideration

This research paper strives to minimize the risk of harm to its target respondents by assuring them of the confidentiality of their responses and ensuring their anonymity throughout the entire research process. At the onset, this researcher secures their free, prior informed consent and assures them of their right to withdraw from their research participation if deemed necessary. No personal data compromising the respondents' identity were collected in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, specifically on accessing the data both by the researcher and the analyst. The respondents are assured that no information that discloses their identity were released or published without their consent, except when extremely necessary. All collected materials were appropriately disposed of by machine shredding or dissolved in water after the study was submitted. At the same time, soft copies of the data were deleted, leaving no chance of future retrieval.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1

Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 36 years old)	55	45.80
	Older (36 years old and above)	65	54.20
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (Elementary Level)	55	45.80
	Higher (High School Level and beyond)	65	54.20
Grade Level	Grade 4	40	33.30
	Grade 5	40	33.30
	Grade 6	40	33.30
Number of Children	Few (less than 3)	55	45.80
	Many (3 and above)	65	54.20
Total		120	100.00

As presented in Table 1, 55, or 45.80%, of the respondents are younger or below 36 years old, while 65, or 54.20%, are older or 36 years old and above. For the highest educational attainment, 55, or 45.80%, of the respondents are elementary graduates, while 65, or 54.20%, of the respondents are high school graduates and above. For variable grade levels, grades 4, 5, and 6 are equally distributed with 40, or 33.33%. Regarding the number of children, 55, or 45.80% of the respondents have few children (below 3), and 65, or 54.20%, have many children (3 and more).

This implies that older parents contributed a larger number of respondents; many of the parents have a higher educational background, are equally distributed in grade level, and most of them have many children. It is said that older parents have better experience in terms of parenting, while parents with higher educational backgrounds may have a better understanding and knowledge of involving children's school activities. Moreover, many children may encounter difficulties in the provision of their children's educational needs. The results are supported by the study conducted by Andalajao (2023) on parental involvement in learners' reading development, wherein the researcher found out that the majority of the research participants are older parents, many of whom have higher educational attainment, and many children.

Table 2

Level of Parental Involvement According to Home Learning Environment.

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a parent, I ensure/provide my children with</i>		
1. conducive learning environment at home.	4.12	High Level
2. a place/area at home to do their assignments and reading activities	3.75	High Level
3. TV and radio to watch and listen to educational programs to help improve our learning.	3.08	Moderate Level
4. enough printed instructional materials such as books, magazines, encyclopedias, etc.	3.17	Moderate Level
5. comfortable reading space with chairs, tables, proper lighting, and ventilation.	3.78	High Level
6. healthy and nutritious foods to boost their memory in learning and reading.	3.58	High Level
7. away from distractions and loud noise while learning at home.	3.32	Moderate Level
8. balance their educational and recreational activities.	3.58	High Level
9. weekly learning and reading routine at home.	3.33	Moderate Level
10. gadgets/devices to be used for doing their homework and assignments.	3.18	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.49	Moderate Level

Table 2 presents the level of parental involvement in the area of the home learning environment. The respondents obtained an overall mean score of 3.49, interpreted as a moderate level.

Going deeper into the analysis, respondents obtained the highest mean score of 4.12 on item No. 1, stating to provide a conducive learning environment at home, interpreted as a high level. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.08 was on item No. 3, stating that providing TV and radio to watch and listen to educational programs to help improve our learning is interpreted as a moderate level.

The findings suggest that a significant number of respondents lack the capacity to provide a conducive home learning environment for their children, especially regarding the availability of support instructional materials like televisions, gadgets, and printed reading resources. This is likely due to the economic conditions of the respondents, wherein the majority of them belonged to an average and low-income worker. Parents must make sure that all of their children have access to the resources they need to improve their learning because students cannot concentrate on their studies and achieve the intended academic results without materials and a comfortable and conducive environment at home.

The finding, supported by Macud (2023), revealed a low parental involvement in the provision of materials, financial support, and other school stuff. Parents are occasionally involved in the provision of materials to their children due to limited income. Also, parents were occasionally involved in the non-material support of parents, such as time, attention, and others, due to their limited time caused by busy work.

Table 3

Level of Parental Involvement According to Parent-Teacher Communication

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a parent, I...</i>		
1. regularly communicate with the teachers and ask for feedback on the performance of my children.	3.24	Moderate Level
2. regularly attend PTA meetings and important activities of the school.	3.86	High Level
3. volunteer and assist teachers with the selected learning and reading activities of the school.	2.99	Moderate Level
4. participates in the preparation and implementation of reading activities of my children	3.41	Moderate Level
5. collaborate with my child's teachers to improve their learning and reading skills.	3.28	Moderate Level
6. appreciates the efforts of the teachers and school heads in educating my children.	3.26	Moderate Level
7. involve decision-making in a child's learning and reading activities in school.	3.22	Moderate Level
8. develop a harmonious partnership with the teachers to promote the learning objectives and goals of the school.	3.19	Moderate Level
9. shares important information with other parents about the learning and reading activities in school.	3.37	Moderate Level
10. cooperates with the teachers in monitoring the attendance and progress of the learners in reading.	3.13	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.29	Moderate Level

Table 3 discloses the results on the level of parental involvement in the area of parent-teacher communication. Respondents obtained an overall mean score of 3.29 and interpreted it as a moderate level.

But for further investigation, the respondents obtained the highest mean score of 3.86 on item No. 2, stating to regularly attend PTA meetings and important activities of the school, interpreted as a high level, while the lowest mean of 2.99 was on item No. 3, stating to volunteer and assist teachers of the selected learning and reading activities of the school, interpreted as a moderate level.

According to the results, the majority of respondents appeared less willing to volunteer and support teachers with certain reading and learning activities at the school. This is due to the fact that parents are already worn out from doing housework, and some parents work throughout the day, which leaves them with less time to devote to their kids' reading activities. Added to this is the misconception of some parents, who believe that it is not their primary responsibility to be involved with their children's schooling but that it is the teacher's responsibility to ensure that their children perform well in school.

The finding is supported by Caranguian (2023), wherein the researcher concluded that if the parents want their children to improve their academic performance and their social adjustment, they have to increase the frequency of contact or communication they have with the teachers of their children, that they take an active role in participating

in the extracurricular activities that their children are involved in at school, and that they provide more support for learning at home.

Table 4

Level of Parental Involvement According to Family Support System

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a parent, I....</i>		
1. financially support my children to join in various school learning and reading activities.	4.09	High Level
2. give reward to my children of their good reading performance in school.	3.57	High Level
3. help guide my children in completing their assignments and homework.	3.63	High Level
4. encourage my child in joining reading intervention activities of the school.	3.75	High Level
5. bring along my children in library, bookstore, and places that help improve their learning and reading skills.	3.05	Moderate Level
6. frequently praise my children for their learning achievement.	3.68	High Level
7. play language games and other educational games with my children as family bonding time.	3.49	High Level
8. talk to my children about their problems and difficulties in school.	3.68	High Level
9. serve as role model to my children for the love of learning and reading.	3.78	High Level
10. motivates my children to do their best in all learning activities of the school.	3.88	High Level
Overall Mean	3.66	High Level

Table 4 divulges the data on the level of parental involvement in the area of the family support system. Respondents obtained an overall mean score of 3.66 and interpreted it as a high level.

However, conducting thorough analysis, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 4.09 on item No. 1, stating to financially support my children to join in various school learning and reading activities, which is interpreted as a very high level, while the lowest mean of 3.05 was on item No. 5, stating to bring along my children to libraries, bookstores, and places that help improve their learning and reading skills, which is interpreted as a moderate level.

The result implies that respondents rarely bring along their children to bookstores and places that help improve their learning and reading skills. The reason is that not all parents have the ability to buy reading books for their children. At the same time, some of the parents were not aware of the role of libraries in children's reading development. Reading could be boring to some children; thus, parents must teach their children in an interesting manner. Family support systems and involvement in school activities such as reading may influence the learners' reading ability.

The finding is supported by Kamuge (2018), wherein the researcher found out that visiting libraries and bookshops with their children, presenting books as presents to children, and collaborating with the teacher influence preschool children's reading interests and reading habits.

Table 5

Level of Learners' Performance for the School Year 2023-2024

Variable	N	Mean	Interpretation
Level of Learners' Performance	120	78.15	Instructional

As presented in the table, the learners obtained an overall performance of 78.15, interpreted as instructional level. In the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI), the instructional level is the level at which a student benefits from teacher-directed reading instruction. The result implies that the reading performance of the learners is only at the instructional level. This means that they still need the guidance and assistance of teachers in reading. Some of the learners still encountered confusion on how to correctly read words. Some also experience difficulties reading unfamiliar words. It suggests that reading teachers continue providing them with reading materials suitable for their needs and grade level and then move to more complex reading texts and those that actually cater to their areas of interest. These can provide avenues for the learners to grow from being instructional readers to becoming independent ones.

The result relates to that of Bohol (2024). The study results showed that the key stage 2 learners showed an instructional level of reading comprehension, particularly in vocabulary, fluency, and word recognition. Likewise,

Calantas (2020) found out that the learners' reading performance in terms of letter knowledge, phonics, and print awareness was only at the instructional level.

Table 6

Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement According to Home Learning Environment When Grouped and Compared According to Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Grade Level, and Number of Children

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	55	67.76	1388.00	.035	0.05	Significant
	Older	65	54.35				
Highest Educational Attainment	Male	55	58.23	1662.50	.509	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	65	64.42				
Number of Children	Few	55	64.54	1565.50	.241	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	65	57.08				

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H Test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Grade Level	Grade 4	40	69.49	11.41	.003	0.05	Significant
	Grade 5	40	66.55				
	Grade 6	40	45.46				

Table 6 summarizes the comparative analysis of the level of parental involvement in the area of the home learning environment when grouped and compared according to age, highest education attainment, number of children, and grade level.

The computed p-values for variables with the highest educational attainment and number of children are 0.509 and 0.241, respectively, which are all greater than 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the area of the home learning environment when grouped and compared according to the highest educational attainment and number of children is accepted.

However, for the variables age and grade level, the computed p-values are 0.035 and 0.003, which are less than 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the area of the home learning environment when grouped and compared according to age and grade level is rejected.

The result implies that the level of parental involvement in the area of the home learning environment varies according to age and grade level. This is because many of the younger parents are less knowledgeable and understand how to facilitate and engage in their children's reading activities at home and in school. On the other hand, parents, particularly in the higher grade level, perceived that it was the responsibility of the teachers to educate their children; hence, they seldom bought learning materials for their children at home.

The finding contradicts that of Germudo (2021), wherein no significant difference existed in the level of parental involvement in the delivery of printed learning modality when compared according to variables.

Table 7

Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement According to Parent-Teacher Communication When Grouped and Compared According to Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Grade Level, and Number of Children

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
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Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H Test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	55	63.92	1599.50	.321	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	65	57.61				
Highest Educational Attainment	Male	55	56.15	1548.00	.206	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	65	64.18				
Number of Children	Few	55	66.18	1475.00	.099	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	65	55.69				
Grade Level	Grade 4	40	75.75	17.29	.000	0.05	Significant
	Grade 5	40	62.16				
	Grade 6	40	43.59				

Table 7 reviews the comparative analysis of the level of parental involvement in the area of parent-teacher communication when grouped and compared according to age, highest education attainment, number of children, and grade level.

The computed p-values for variables age, highest educational attainment, and number of children are 0.321, 0.206, and 0.099, respectively, which are all greater than 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the area of parent-teacher communication when grouped and compared according to age, highest educational attainment, and number of children is accepted.

However, for the variable grade level, the computed p-value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the area of parent-teacher communication when grouped and compared according to grade level is rejected.

The result implies that the level of parental involvement in the area of parent-teacher communication varies according to grade level. Parents in the higher grade level rarely communicate and pass all the responsibilities to the teachers. Parents are confident enough to entrust to the teachers the child's discipline and academic performance, thinking their child has a higher sense of responsibility at this grade level. Meanwhile, parents in the lower grades regularly communicate with their children's teachers. This can also be seen during PTA meetings, wherein the attendance of the parents in the lower grade level is almost present while parents in the higher grade level are absent. The finding contradicts that of Caranguian (2023), wherein professional parents have a very different level of involvement in their children's education compared with non-professional parents. Women in professional roles have a participation rate that is noticeably greater than that of their peers. If parents want their children to improve their academic performance and their social adjustment, it is recommended that they increase the frequency of contact or communication they have with the teachers of their children, and that they take an active role in participating in the extracurricular activities that their children are involved in at school, and that they provide more support for learning at home.

Table 8

Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement According to Family Support System When Grouped and Compared According to Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Grade Level, and Number of Children

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	55	57.65	1631.00	.372	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	65	62.91				
Highest Educational Attainment	Male	55	57.65	1631.00	.372	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	65	62.91				
	Few	55	62.49	1678.00	.532	0.05	Not Significant

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H Test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Grade Level	Grade 4	40	70.85	6.492	.039	0.05	Significant
	Grade 5	40	53.54				
	Grade 6	40	57.11				

Table 8 analyzes the comparative analysis of the level of parental involvement in the area of the family support system when grouped and compared according to age, highest education attainment, number of children, and grade level.

The computed p-values for variables age, highest educational attainment, and number of children are 0.372, 0.372, and 0.532, respectively, which are all greater than 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the area of the family support system when grouped and compared according to age, highest educational attainment, and number of children is accepted.

However, for the variable grade level, the computed p-value is 0.039, which is less than 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the area of the family support system when grouped and compared according to grade level is rejected.

The result implies that the level of parental involvement in the area of family support systems varies according to grade level. This is because parents with children in the higher grade level gave less attention to their child's school activities, believing that their child could manage independently, and were convinced that their child was responsible enough at a certain age to muddle through. Parents with children in the lower grades paid more attention as they believed that their children still needed assistance with school-related activities. An unescapable concern dwells in every parent, sensing how juvenile the learners are. The result contradicts that of Macud (2023), wherein there was no significant difference in the extent of parental involvement when they were grouped according to occupation and family size. However, there was a significant difference in the extent of parental involvement due to educational qualifications.

Table 9

Relationship Between the Level of Parental Involvement and the Level of Learners' Performance for the School Year 2023-2024

Correlates	N	<i>rho</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Level of Sig	Interpretation
Level of Parental Involvement	120	0.570	0.00	0.05	Significant
Level of Learners' Performance	120				

As presented in the table, the obtained *rho* was 0.570 with a *p*-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the level of parental involvement and the level of learners' performance was therefore rejected.

The finding implies that the level of parental support significantly influences learners' reading performance. This means that the higher the involvement of parents in a child's school activities, the higher the performance their child can perform. Learners tend to perform better in school, earn higher grades, score higher on tests, and obtain a higher level of competence in reading passages, which could lead to acquiring the skills to succeed academically through the consistent involvement of the parents. The finding is supported by that of Mugumya et al. (2022), wherein parents' provision of a good learning environment at home positively predicted students' academic performance. Parents' direct participation in knowing what their students' study in some subjects and encouragement to study at home would be beneficial to the children's academic progress. Likewise, Naranjo (2019) revealed a significant relationship between the involvement of parents in reading activities and pupils' reading performance. The more parents' involvement in reading activities, the higher the possibility of children attaining a higher level of reading performance, word recognition and comprehension, and favorable attitudes towards school.

Conclusions

The study found that most respondents were older parents with high school education or higher and many children, with equal distribution across grade levels. Parental involvement was moderate in the areas of home learning environment and parent-teacher communication, and high in family support systems. Learners' performance was at the instructional level, with a significant relationship between parental involvement and student performance. It was also found that parental involvement in the home learning environment varied by age, and that parents of higher grade level students tended to be more involved. The study concluded that parental involvement, especially in family support systems, positively influenced learners' performance, though improvement was needed in the home learning environment and parent-teacher communication. Recommendations include providing better learning materials at home, increasing parent-teacher interactions, enhancing school support systems, and involving parents more in school activities. Furthermore, teachers and school heads should focus on creating a welcoming environment for parents, offer consistent reading activities, and collaborate with local institutions to improve access to learning resources.

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